

Quadruple Band Slot Antenna with Double L-Shaped Slot Etching Technique

Watcharaphon Naktong, Piyadanai Boonmaitree and
Supatinee Korsing

Department of Telecommunication Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering and Architecture
Rajamangala University of Technology Isan (RMUTI)
744, Suranaray Road, Nakhon Ratchasima, Thailand
oachi525@gmail.com

Amnoiy Ruengwaree

Department of Electronics and Telecommunication
Engineering, Faculty of Engineering
Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi
(RMUTT)
39, Rangsit-Nakhonnayok Road, Pathum Thani, Thailand
amnoiy.r@en.rmutt.ac.th

Abstract— This article presents a quadruple band microstrip antenna with L-shaped slot etching technique for WLAN/WiMAX applications. The universal antenna inherits with large size and complex structure. This work tackles these two drawbacks by applying double L-shaped slot etching technique. The design was carried and verified by using a commercial program, CST. Critical parameters with appropriated characteristics was fine tuned to reach satisfaction. Finally, the designed antenna was fabricated and characterized. The fabricated antenna possesses quadruple band frequency response at 2.46 GHz (2.38 - 2.55 GHz), 3.48 GHz (3.42-3.59GHz), 5.19 GHz (5.11 - 5.32 GHz) and 5.81 GHz (5.62-5.87GHz) corresponding with IEEE 802.11b/g and IEEE 802.16 a/e.

Keywords— Return loss, WLAN/ WiMAX, Microstrip

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, wireless communication with specific band is popularly applied in navigation systems, underground object detection, object detection and communication for short receiving - sending data etc. [1-2]. Antenna is an important element for these applications; however, the conventional antenna inherits with several drawbacks such as large size and limited frequency band selections [3-6]. Microstrip antenna [7] offers advantages particularly in term of scale size of an antenna. This work proposed a microstrip antenna for quadruple band special frequency response with small size of antenna structure. The desired characters and size reduction were achieved by using L-shaped slot etching. The characteristics of designed antenna, return loss, Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR), gain and radiation pattern of antenna were simulated by a commercial program, CST. The fabrication of the designed antenna was made and measured.

II. EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS

This The prototype antenna was fabricated on a print circuit board with FR4 base with the constant dielectric value of (ϵ_r) 4.3 and the thickness (h) of 0.764 mm by the original antenna size as 40×40 mm² as show in Fig. 1. The experimental results show in Fig. 2, from the experiment result shows that return loss of measured result comparing with the CST simulation.

Fig. 1 Fabricated antenna

Fig. 2 Simulation and measurement of return loss

The radiation pattern at frequency of 2.46 GHz, 3.48 GHz, 5.19 GHz and 5.81 GHz between the simulation and fabrication were compared and showed in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. Electric field (E-plane) wave radiation as shown in Fig. 3 reveal a good agreement of a radiation pattern in x-z plane of both simulation and experiment. Similarly, the magnetic radiation (H-plane) in x-z plane also show the similar pattern of simulation VS experiment as shown in Fig. 4. In the part of

magnetic radiation (H-plane) is directivity which show in x-z plane as Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Radiation Pattern at 2.46 GHz, 3.48 GHz 5.19 GHz and 5.81 GHz on E-plane

Fig. 4 Radiation Pattern at 2.46 GHz, 3.48 GHz 5.19 GHz and 5.81 GHz on H-plane

III. CONCLUSION

This work achieved the design and fabrication of a quadruple band microstrip antenna with double L-shaped slot etching technique. The 4th band of 5.2 GHz was added without interference to other working frequencies in the standard range of IEEE 802.11b/g 2.4 GHz (2.4 - 2.4835 GHz), IEEE 802.16e 3.5 GHz (3.4 - 3.69 GHz), IEEE.802.16a 5.2 GHz (5.13 - 5.35 GHz) and 5.8 GHz (5.7 - 5.9 GHz) [1-2]. The simulation and experimental results measured from the fabrication exhibit the ability to support 4 standard frequency bands of 2.46 GHz (2.38 - 2.55 GHz) 3.48 GHz (3.42 - 3.59 GHz) 5.19 GHz (5.11 - 5.32 GHz) and 5.81 GHz (5.62 - 5.87 GHz).

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE 802.11, "Wireless Access Method and Physical Layer Specifications," New York, NY, USA, September 1994.
- [2] B. O. Hara and A. Petrick, The IEEE 802.11 Handbook: A Designer's Companion, IEEE Press, New York, NY, USA, 1999.
- [3] A. A. Eldek, C. M. Allen, A. Z. Elsherbeni, C. E. Smith and Kai-Fong Lee, "Slot Antennas for Dual and Wideband Operation in Wireless Communication Systems", IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine, vol. no. 44, 2002.
- [4] A. I. Abunjaileh, I. C. Hunter and A. H. Kemp, "Multi-band Matching Technique for Microstrip Patch Antenna Transceivers," Proceedings of the 37th Microwave Conference, 2007, European, Munich, Germany, pp. 254-257, 9-12 October 2007.
- [5] S. Sakulchat and A. Ruengwaree, "Dual Band Microstrip Antenna with Triangular Tuning Stub for WLAN Applications," Antennas, Propagation and EM Theory, 2008. ISAPE 2008. 8th International Symposium on, pp. 546-549, 2-5 November 2008.
- [6] P. Rakkua, N. Anantrasirichai, K. Janchitrapongvej, and T. Wakabayashi, "Multiband Microstrip-Fed Right Angle Slot Antenna Design for Wireless Communication Systems," Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute (ETRI) Journal, Volume 31, Number 3, June 2009.
- [7] P. Chaiboon, A. Namsang, "Double Rectangular Grooves Microstrip Antenna With The Dual L-shape Tuning Stubs Supporting Tri-Band Frequencies", International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation (ISAP 2011), Macao, China, 23-26 November 2011.